

IMPACT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON LEADERSHIP TRAITS AMONG REGIONAL PARTY LEADERS USING STEPWISE LINEAR REGRESSION METHOD

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Abstract

The regional political parties have significantly developed over years and transformed into potential for sustenance. The leadership traits have significantly contributed and as a result, after independence, the statistics reveal that more than 30% of the votes in the national elections are won by the regional parties. In the present research study, a critical examination is made to study the leadership traits in the emergence and sustenance of regional political parties in India. Emotional intelligence is emerged as one of the most vibrant dimension influencing the leadership effectiveness especially in regional political system. Since, majority of the leaders deals with regional issues, the emotional intelligence has significant impact on leadership traits of the leaders. In this connection, the paper emphasize on evaluating the leadership effectiveness of the leaders with special reference to impact of impact of select leadership dimensions on Emotional Intelligence using Stepwise Linear Regression method.

Keywords: *Effectiveness, Emotional Intelligence, Step Wise Linear Regression, Traits.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Leadership is the life organ for the success or failure of sustainability of parties. A leader possesses distinctive qualities which help him to lead the party. Leaders in the present era have been facing stiff competition to cope up with globalization, rising entry of new leaders, and adoption to latest trends in technology. Effective leadership tackles the complexities arising in the party. Effective leadership creates the vision that the party cadre wishes to achieve. The inspiring nature of the leader will enhance the spirit of the party cadre and supports the achievement of the vision of the party. The leaders act as change agents and the disrupting nature of leadership makes them be unique in society.

The leadership possesses distinctive qualities such as the ability to take risk will make them supreme in the party. The political leadership needs an effective leader to concentrate on nation's benefits as primary importance and thinks personal goals as less important. Political leadership concentrates on the allocation of power and value through effective governance of politics, establishing partnerships with stake holders and taking decisions that will reflect the nation's well being and contributes to reputation to the party. The emerging leadership requires

focusing on long term betterment of nation's progress and requires a set of leadership qualities and capacities which make the leader be an effective performer

2. CONCEPTUAL OVERVIEW OF LEADERSHIP

The term "leader" was been in practice since 1300 A.D. The leader term was used as a synonym for Commander, Ruler, King, Chief. Leadership is termed as a process which integrates group, determines the effects of leaders through his personality. Leadership is further regarded as power relation and exercising of influence for the achievement of goals. Leadership is often differentiated among the leaders due to the type of initiation, act, or behavior of the leaders.

According to Tennenbaum "Leadership is the interpersonal influence exercised in a situation and directed through the Interpersonal relationship process, towards the attainment of a specified goal or goals". A leader is someone who has followers who work under his leadership (Drucker P). The leader will have the capacity to translate the vision set for the party into reality (Bennis W). Roosevelt F.D. has opined that the political leader's commitment towards public rely on the efficiency of leader who can largely influence and ensure the public realizes their goals.

The leader's role will be empowering others through effective leadership qualities (Bill Gates) and the leadership strongly influences the vision of the party and the leader is a dealer of hope (Napolean). Wayne Paines has described the leader as someone who has the ability to comprehend one's own feelings and works accordingly. According to the definition specified in Business Dictionary (2015), the leadership involves creating a vision and sharing the vision to others to be followed and further sharing the knowledge and information to others in order to ensure that they realize the vision. Kruse (2013) has defined leadership as "a process of influencing the society to increase the efforts of the followers for the realization of goals. The leadership definition given by Kruse more specifically focused on social influence. Barnard Key has mentioned that, "Leadership is the process of influencing and supporting others to work enthusiastically toward achieving objectives". Based on the functional performance of leader, the leaders can be differentiated as Formal leader, Informal leader, Democratic Leader, Intellectual leader, Autocratic Leader, Creative leader etc.

3. STUDY ON EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN LEADERSHIP

A study conducted by Bakshi (2018) reveals that the Emotional intelligence capabilities of 247 corporate leaders resulted in the following form of leadership styles. The author has found that, under self with confidence and Transparency, the leader develops visionary strength and maintaining self-awareness and self-management competencies.

Under emotional self-awareness capability, the leader develops the strength of coaching and prepares self-awareness competency. Under Empathy capability, the leader develops social awareness and develops the leadership style as coaching. Under inspirational leadership, the leader develops a visionary form of leadership with competencies focusing on Relationship Management. Under Change Catalyst and developing others capabilities, the leader develops competencies in Relationship management.

Leadership Style	Impact	Description
VISIONARY	+++	Leads people towards a shared vision
COACHING	++	Enables leaders to build capability in individuals
AFFILIATIVE	+	Provides cohesiveness and harmony to a team, group or organisation
DEMOCRATIC	+	Builds engagement, commitment and buy-in
PACE-SETTING	--	Sets high standards by expecting followers to "do as I do" and to set meet targets
COMMANDING	---	Demands immediate compliance to a leader's agenda and decisions

Figure 1: Bakshi's Model of Leadership style

The Emotional intelligence focus on the abilities of the leader to understand, evaluate and manage the emotions in such a manner that will reflect his decision-making.

The term Emotional intelligence pertaining to Leadership was first coined by John Mayer and Peter Salovey(1990), later the concepts of emotional intelligence are popularized by Daniel Goleman, the famous psychologist. The study on Emotional intelligence published in Harvard Business Review reveals that the emotional intelligence is different to Intelligence quotient and the skills required for a leader to manage things will be supported by emotional intelligence.

4. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

LeaderShape (2011) report explained about transpersonal leadership style. According to the report, transpersonal leadership focuses beyond personal egos and extending individual strengths and abilities to be ethical, radical and authentic in his style and delivers decisions through emotional intelligence.

Petroff R (2015) has conducted a study to analyze the leadership traits of adaptability related to the effectiveness of leadership. The author has further compared the relationship between leadership effectiveness and leadership traits for public and private sectors. In his study, the author has opined that the traits related to leadership effectiveness are significantly differing for various sectors.

Nobrega S (2019) in his study has analyzed leadership and emotional intelligence with a special focus on Venezuela. The author has explained the seniority of uncertainty caused due to lack of effective leadership and further the author has explained how an individual to balance the uncertainties through emotional intelligence. Landry L (2019) in her study has focused on the dimensions of emotional intelligence. The author has further explained the significance of a leader for the organization. The author has stated that the leaders lacking emotional intelligence have to face the consequences in terms of failure in achieving the goals.

The study on literature reveals that, most of the studies were focused on the emergence, growth of regional political parties and impact of leadership on the sustenance of political parties. The literature further reveals that there is a research gap with special reference to leadership traits influence on regional parties and emotional intelligence of leadership towards the growth and prosperity of regional parties.

5. OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

1. To study the key dimensions influencing the leadership using select model.
2. To analyze Emerging Factors influenced Regional Political parties.
3. To examine the characteristics of Emotional Intelligence of Leaders of Regional Political Parties
4. To present the impact of select leadership dimensions on Emotional Intelligence using Stepwise Linear Regression method.

6. METHODOLOGY

Detailed presentation of selection of sample size, results of Reliability and sampling method applied is presented here.

a) Collection of Data: The sources of Data include primary sources of data and Secondary sources of Data. Primary source of data is obtained from sample respondents from two select sample states covering about 4 districts. Secondary sources of data is obtained from literature obtained from articles, journals, news papers and published and unpublished data extracted from web sources.

b) Sample Size and Sampling Method: The sample respondents are public and leaders of select regional political parties. The sample respondents pertaining to public segment are drawn using Multi-stage purposive Sampling Method. In the first stage, the required sample respondents are drawn from two select states, i.e., Andhra Pradesh and Telangana States. In the second stage, from the two states, two districts from each region are selected.

From Andhra Pradesh state, Erstwhile Kurnool District is selected from Rayalaseema region. From Coastal Andhra Region, Erstwhile Krishna District is selected. From Telangana state, Erstwhile Warangal is selected from Northern Telangana region and Hyderabad is selected from Southern Telangana Region. From each district, a sample of 100 respondents is selected through purposive sampling. Altogether the total sample size is 400 respondents representing 200 from Andhra Pradesh state and 200 from Telangana state.

The sample size meets the 5% confidence interval and 95 % confidence interval for determining the sample size in case of undetermined population size. The sample study is restricted to two select states with a vision to analyze the emergence of select political parties and the perception of public on the leadership traits of the select regional political parties. Results are shown in table-1.

Table1: Distribution of Sample Size

Sl. No.	State category	Region	Select District	Sample
1.	Andhra Pradesh	Coastal Andhra	Erstwhile Krishna District	100
		Rayalaseema	Erstwhile Kurnool District	100
2.	Telangana	Northern Telangana	Erstwhile Warangal District	100
		Southern Telangana	Erstwhile Rangareddy District	100
	Total respondents	4 regions	4 districts	400

The Cronbach's ' α ' value is estimated to inspect the internal consistency between the variables tested in experiment. In above table the Alpha attained the value 0.992 i.e., $\alpha > 0.7$ show the extreme internal consistency in between the variables defined in test, this produce a strong base to conduct research on proposed study. Validity test is conducted to test how well the proposed variables defined in study are covered the areas concerned to the proposed research study, the inter item correlated values of said variables are significant at five percent level and positively correlated to each other, Hence the elements designed in test are valid and provide base to support for conducting an effective data analysis based on objectives defined in research study.

7. ANALYSIS ON EMERGING FACTORS INFLUENCED REGIONAL POLITICAL PARTIES

With a view to examine the evaluation on emergence of regional political parties in India with special reference to select parties, the sample respondents are asked to respond on factors that have been emerging as most influencing factors for the establishment of regional parties in India with special reference to select states.

Table 2: Characteristics of Emerging Factors

S. No	Emerging Factors	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative %
1	Language	121	30.25	30.25
2	Regional Culture	124	31.00	61.25
3	Economic Backwardness	99	24.75	86.00
4	Religion & Cast	13	3.25	89.25
5	Geographical Factors	43	10.75	100.00
	Total	400	100.00	

Source: Field Study

The table -2 stated above identified the emerging factors considered for establishing the regional parties in India. The present analysis considered five important emerging factors initiating to establish regional parties in India. The emergence factors recognized in present study are Language, Regional Culture, Economic Backwardness, Religion & Cast and Geographical factors.

The regional culture is the primary emerging factors motivating the political leaders to establish Regional parties. 124 respondents, i.e., approximately 31% have opined regional culture is influencing the leaders to start political party. The second primary factor is identified as Language is supported by 121 respondents i.e., 30.25% are preferring regional parties based on their proximity to their local language importance given by the regional parties. Economic Backwardness is the another key factor exercised by the regional parties. This factor contribution is identified as 24.75% of influence on overall. The least scored emerging factor identified as Religion and Caste with the contribution of 3.25% on overall.

8. ANALYSIS ON DIMENSIONS OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF LEADERS

Results of mean score obtained after consolidating the perception scores obtained from the respondents are segmented into 13 dimensions and dimension wise mean score, standard deviation and assigned rank is presented in table-3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Emotional Intelligence Factors

S. No	Emotional Intelligence Factor	Mean	SD	Rank
1	For a leader, promise and action must be in coherence.	3.88	1.332	1
2	Leader must able to look at issues from others point of view	3.88	1.361	2
3	Though act locally, leader should aware of society scenario	3.87	1.327	3
4	Observing regional developments and getting awareness is necessary.	3.81	1.304	4
5	He should stand up for his party men and leaders and also able to scold them if the situation is warranted	3.79	1.309	5
6	Important aspects need to be confidential in politics	3.66	1.293	6
7	People automatically support leader's political interest, if he takes care of their welfare.	3.63	1.297	7
8	Should have extensive network and relations.	3.53	1.288	8
9	Accepting mistakes enhances the leader's image.	3.53	1.288	8
10	It is no wrong to express his emotions	3.36	1.289	10
11	Leader should not ventilate his emotions	3.35	1.318	11
12	Trust prevails competence in leader	3.21	1.295	12
13	Competence prevails trust in leader.	3.02	1.316	13

Source: Field Study

Based on the mean values obtained from the survey, it is to understand that, a mean value of 13 factors is computed. The comparison of mean value for each of the individual dimension shows that, highest mean value equals to 3.88 is noticed in case of coherence nature of promise and action. Equal mean score is also observed in case of leader looking at issues from others point of view. Awareness, observing regional developments, party men nature obtained mean scores equal to 3.87, 3.81 and 3.79 respectively. The important aspects, support, extensive network, accepting mistakes follows the mean scores equal to 3.66, 3.63, 3.53 and 3.53 respectively. With regard to expressing emotions, ventilating emotions, competences, trust, the mean scores equal to 3.36, 3.35, 3.21 and 3.02 are noticed. Overall the highest mean score leads to rank 1 and rank 2 are assigned promising nature and empathy nature of leadership. The comparison of standard deviations reveal that, highest variation is noticed in case of empathy and least variation is noticed in case of extensive network and accepting nature of leaders. Overall, the study show that leaders have perceived higher pertaining to promising and empathy factors and least ranks are noticed in case of trust and competence.

5.2.3 Linear Regression on Leadership dimensions

The present analysis enhances the different dimensions/traits of the leaders of regional parties. This study extracted the opinions from the informants about the traits of regional party leaders. The study identified the eighteen different dimensions of leaders and estimated their effectiveness in dealing the issues related to public. The opinion of attitudes of the leaders is estimated using the regression analysis. The factors identified as the dimensions of leaders are Astuteness, Strategy, Statesmanship, Transparency, Relationship Management, Accountability, Creativity, Command,

Interpersonal relationship, Command, Courage, Crisis- Management, Decision Making, Knowledge, Intelligence, Self-Management, Lead by example and Emotional Intelligence of leaders. A Hierarchical linear regression is tested among the dimension stated above, the model established the different forms of linear regression equations based on their test static occurrences. The experiment takes into the consideration of all elements and identified formed the linearity among the consider response and predictor elements. The stepwise model of regression exhibits the importance of variables in equation in a chronological order and determine their intensity on overall experiment with identified standardized and Unstandardized co-efficient and their intercepting constant values. The following hypothesis is tested under Linear Regression Model

H₀₆: Emotional Intelligence of leader is not influence by the other dimensions.

Table 4: Model Summary of Regression Analysis on Emotional Intelligence

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	SEE
1	.982	.964	.964	.221
2	.985	.971	.971	.197
3	.987	.973	.973	.190
4	.988	.976	.976	.179
5	.989	.978	.978	.173
6	.990	.980	.980	.164
7	.991	.983	.982	.154
8	.991	.983	.982	.153

Source: Field Study

The Table-4 depicts the different models formed by conducting linear regression equation. As per the statement mentioned at the beginning of experiment the different forms eighteen dimension are taken into consideration for fitting the model of regression. The regression equations are formed among the dimensions are equivalent to eight. By looking into the numeric values of model summary it is clear the regression experiment co-efficient values are more than 0.9 this declare the high positive correlation is extracted between the elements formed under regression model. The high co-efficient correlation existed for the both model seven and eight is 0.991. The low correlation 0.982 is identified for the model one. The adjusted R² for the model seven eight is extreme compare to rest of model i.e., 0.982 it explains the maximum variance of dependent and independent variables in the model is 98.2%. This percentile of variance is an indicator for a strong linear formation between the elements. The low adjusted R² is located for the initial model of regression equation.

Analysis on F- test values of linear Regression Equation

The table -4 depicts the F static values of linear regression equation, the experiment of linearity stated above formed eight different regression model by considering the variables given as inputs. The test values of above ANOVA experiment identified the probabilistic values to locate the impact of the stated dependent variable ‘Emotional Intelligence’ and other nine independent variables like Astuteness, strategy, statesmanship, Transparency, Relationship Management, Accountability, Creativity and Command. The eight different models are formed in hierarchical order to form regression among the variables tested in experiment. The regression analysis is conducted to identify of intensity of “Emotional Intelligence” on other stated dimensions considered as predictors.

Table 5: ANOVA Table of Regression Equation

	Model	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
1	Regression	516.443	1	516.443	10603.334	.000
	Residual	19.385	398	.049		
	Total	535.828	399			
2	Regression	520.379	2	260.190	6686.369	.000
	Residual	15.449	397	.039		
	Total	535.828	399			
3	Regression	521.545	3	173.848	4819.950	.000
	Residual	14.283	396	.036		
	Total	535.828	399			
4	Regression	523.176	4	130.794	4083.462	.000
	Residual	12.652	395	.032		
	Total	535.828	399			
5	Regression	524.025	5	104.805	3498.527	.000
	Residual	11.803	394	.030		
	Total	535.828	399			
6	Regression	525.224	6	87.537	3244.445	.000
	Residual	10.603	393	.027		
	Total	535.828	399			
7	Regression	526.541	7	75.220	3175.144	.000
	Residual	9.287	392	.024		
	Total	535.828	399			
8	Regression	526.632	8	65.829	2799.110	.000
	Residual	9.195	391	.024		
	Total	535.828	399			
Dependent Variable: Emotional Intelligence Predictors: (Constant), Astuteness, Strategy, Statesmanship, Transparency, Relationship Management, Accountability, Creativity, Command						

Source: Field Study

In hierarchical order the variable dependent is tested by considered the predictor variables Astuteness in first model and chronologically each model from second to eighth model the experiment added one by one predictor variables in model. The first model is tested the significance between Emotional intelligence and Astuteness and this process is continuing till the end of eighth model by adding one independent in each model, the last model i.e., eighth model of linear regression equation is developed by considering the dependent ‘Emotional-intelligence’ and predictor variables of regression model “Astuteness, Strategy, Statesmanship, Relationship-Management, Accountability, Transparency, Creativity and Command. From the ‘F’ Table The highest MS is identified for model one is 516.443 and low level mean is reached for the model eight is 65.829 The decrease MS value indicated a chronological value of decrease in F value. From the Table 5.36 the noteworthy test values for all eight models are arrived at 0.000 at $\alpha = 0.05$ at five percent LOS. This can be written as $p < 0.05$ and provide a ground for strong evidence to accepting the alternative hypothesis and disowning the statement of ‘Null Hypothesis’. The ANOVA experiment result consolidate the statement for all stated eight variables of independents are showing impact on overall emotional intelligence of leaders of regional rural parties.

Table 6: Analysis on Regression Co-efficients

Model		UC		SC	t	P-value
		B	SE	β		
1	(Constant)	.079	.036		2.222	.027
	Astuteness	.965	.009	.982	102.972	.000
2	(Constant)	.032	.032		.976	.330
	Astuteness	.812	.017	.826	46.666	.000
	Strategy	.187	.019	.178	10.058	.000
3	(Constant)	.022	.031		.697	.486
	Astuteness	.779	.018	.793	44.022	.000
	Strategy	.153	.019	.145	8.087	.000
	statesmanship	.072	.013	.079	5.685	.000
4	(Constant)	.027	.029		.934	.351
	Astuteness	.745	.017	.758	42.943	.000
	Strategy	.222	.020	.211	10.944	.000
	statesmanship	.094	.012	.104	7.661	.000
	Transparency	-.066	.009	-.080	-7.136	.000
5	(Constant)	.033	.028		1.161	.246
	Astuteness	.630	.027	.641	23.063	.000
	Strategy	.178	.021	.169	8.352	.000
	statesmanship	.102	.012	.112	8.487	.000
	Transparency	-.059	.009	-.071	-6.462	.000
	Relationship Management	.139	.026	.149	5.323	.000
6	(Constant)	.026	.027		.953	.341
	Astuteness	.553	.028	.562	19.451	.000
	Strategy	.225	.021	.214	10.511	.000
	statesmanship	.126	.012	.139	10.548	.000
	Transparency	-.066	.009	-.080	-7.605	.000
	Relationship Management	.295	.034	.315	8.654	.000
	Accountability	-.141	.021	-.156	-6.668	.000
7	(Constant)	.013	.025		.528	.598
	Astuteness	.502	.028	.510	18.245	.000
	Strategy	.227	.020	.215	11.294	.000
	statesmanship	.125	.011	.138	11.211	.000
	Transparency	-.097	.009	-.117	-10.607	.000
	Relationship Management	.330	.032	.352	10.224	.000
	Accountability	-.169	.020	-.187	-8.395	.000
	Creativity	.080	.011	.087	7.455	.000
8	(Constant)	.018	.025		.724	.469
	Astuteness	.516	.028	.525	18.213	.000
	Strategy	.221	.020	.210	10.912	.000
	statesmanship	.132	.012	.146	11.316	.000
	Transparency	-.095	.009	-.114	-10.324	.000
	Relationship Management	.339	.032	.362	10.438	.000
	Accountability	-.152	.022	-.168	-6.927	.000
	Creativity	.076	.011	.083	7.098	.000
	Command	-.042	.022	-.044	-1.968	.045

Dependent Variable: Emotional Intelligence
 Predictors: (Constant), Astuteness, Strategy, Statesmanship, Transparency, Relationship Management, Accountability, Creativity, Command

Source: Field Study

The table-6 explain the different forms of linear regressions formed using hierarchical method, the table illustrate the eight different regression models formed by considering the different types of dimensions. The table numeric disclosed the regression co-efficient statistics between the dependent variable “Emergence Factors” and Independent variables of rest of the dimensions or traits of the leaders.

I. Analysis on Regression Equation based on Model One

The regression equation formulated under model one is

$$\text{Emotion Intelligence} = \text{Constant} + B (\text{Astuteness})$$

$$\text{Emotion Intelligence} = 0.079 + 0.965 (\text{Astuteness})$$

II. Analysis on Model Two of Regression Equation

The linear equation formed under model two is

$$\text{Emotion Intelligence} = \text{Constant} + B_1 (\text{Astuteness}) + B_2 (\text{strategy})$$

$$\text{Emotion Intelligence} = 0.032 + 0.812 (\text{Astuteness}) + 0.187 (\text{strategy})$$

III. Analysis on Regression Equation based on Model Three

The equation formed using coefficients is as follows

$$\text{Emotion Intelligence} = \text{Constant} + B_1 (\text{Astuteness}) + B_2 (\text{strategy}) + B_3 (\text{statesmanship})$$

$$\text{EI} = 0.022 + 0.779 (\text{Astuteness}) + 0.153 (\text{strategy}) + 0.072 (\text{statesmanship})$$

(EI = Emotional Intelligence)

IV. Analysis on Model Four Regression Equation

The Regression Equation developed based on the experiment model four can be expressed as follows

$$\text{EI} = \text{Constant} + B_1 (\text{Astuteness}) + B_2 (\text{strategy}) + B_3 (\text{statesmanship}) + B_4 (\text{Transparency})$$

$$\text{EI} = 0.027 + 0.745 (\text{Astuteness}) + 0.222 (\text{strategy}) + 0.094 (\text{statesmanship}) - 0.066 (\text{Transparency})$$

V. Analysis on Model Five Regression Equation

The Equation formed under this model is

$$\text{EI} = \text{Constant} + B_1 (\text{Astuteness}) + B_2 (\text{strategy}) + B_3 (\text{statesmanship}) + B_4 (\text{Transparency})$$

$$+ B_5 (\text{Relationship Management})$$

$$\text{EI} = 0.033 + 0.630 (\text{Astuteness}) + 0.178 (\text{strategy}) + 0.102 (\text{statesmanship}) - 0.059 (\text{Transparency})$$

$$+ 0.139 (\text{Relationship Management})$$

VI. Analysis on Model Six of Regression Equation

The equation extracted from the experiment is

$$\text{EI} = \text{Constant} + B_1 (\text{Astuteness}) + B_2 (\text{strategy}) + B_3 (\text{statesmanship}) + B_4 (\text{Transparency})$$

$$+ B_5 (\text{Relationship Management}) + B_6 (\text{Accountability})$$

$$\text{EI} = 0.026 + 0.553 (\text{Astuteness}) + 0.225 (\text{strategy}) + 0.126 (\text{statesmanship}) - 0.066 (\text{Transparency})$$

+ 0.295(Relationship Management) – 0.141 (Accountability)

VII. Analysis on Regression Equation Model Seven

The fitted regression equation formed based on this model seven as

$$EI = \text{Constant} + B_1 (\text{Astuteness}) + B_2 (\text{strategy}) + B_3 (\text{statesmanship}) + B_4 (\text{Transparency}) + B_5 (\text{Relationship Management}) + B_6 (\text{Accountability}) + B_7 (\text{Creativity})$$

$$EI = 0.013 + 0.502 (\text{Astuteness}) + 0.227 (\text{strategy}) + 0.125 (\text{statesmanship}) - 0.097(\text{Transparency}) + 0.330(\text{Relationship Management}) - 169 (\text{Accountability}) + 0.080 (\text{Creativity})$$

VIII. Analysis on Regression Equation Model Eight

This is the final model of regression analysis designed from the experiment conducted above. This model tested to notify the impact of independent variables of eight dimensions and dependent variable Emotional Intelligence. In this model the predictor variables are transparency, Astuteness, statesmanship, strategy, accountability, creativity, relationship management, accountability and command. The probabilistic value determined from the experiment is 0.00 at five percent significance i.e., p is less than 0.05. It is confirmed from the test static value that there is a strong influence of seven dimensions on Emotional intelligence. The significant arrived for dimension command is 0.045 i.e., $p < 0.05$ identifies there is weak influence command on Emotional Intelligence. At the end the test result of model eight states the dimensions considered in experiment are shown impact on Emotional Intelligence.

The Regression Equation designed from the mode eight as follows

$$EI = \text{Constant} + B_1 (\text{Astuteness}) + B_2 (\text{strategy}) + B_3 (\text{statesmanship}) + B_4 (\text{Transparency}) + B_5 (\text{Relationship Management}) + B_6 (\text{Accountability}) + B_7 (\text{Creativity}) + B_8 (\text{Command})$$

$$EI = 0.018 + 0.516 (\text{Astuteness}) + 0.221 (\text{strategy}) + 0.132 (\text{statesmanship}) - 0.095 (\text{Transparency}) + 0.339(\text{Relationship Management}) - 0.152 (\text{Accountability}) + 0.076 (\text{Creativity}) - 0.042 (\text{Command})$$

IX. Analysis on Excluded Variable in Model:

Table 7: Excluded Variables in Regression Analysis

Model	β	t	P-value	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics	
					Tolerance	
8	Interpersonal relationship	.010	.664	.507	.034	.178
	Command	.003	.178	.859	.009	.131
	Courage	-.040	-1.274	.203	-.064	.044
	Crisis- Management	.013	.877	.381	.044	.200
	Decision Making	.002	.111	.912	.006	.168
	Knowledge	.020	1.827	.068	.092	.348
	Intelligence	-.040	-1.450	.148	-.073	.057
	Self-Management	.015	.930	.353	.047	.166
	Lead by example	.026	.875	.382	.044	.050

Dependent Variable: Emotional Intelligence
 Predictors in the Model: (Constant), Astuteness, Strategy, statesmanship, Transparency, Relationship Management, Accountability, Creativity, Command

Source: Field Study

Interpretation: The table-7 demonstrate the excluded variables from the hierarchical model of regression, the excluded variables are eliminated from the fitted regression equation based on their collinearity statistics based on tolerance and significant value more than 0.05 at five percent significance level.

The negative Betas are arrived for the excluded elements of Interpersonal relationship, courage and Intelligence. A high correlation is achieved for Knowledge is 0.92 and the extreme negative correlation is arrived for variable courage is -0.064. As stated at the beginning of experiment eighteen dimensions are identified for leaders and tested the impact of rest of the dimensions on Emotional Intelligence.

The variables eliminated from the model based on two assumptions the primary one is the tolerance identified for the factors is less than 0.2 and second one is based on remarkable test value more than 0.05 at five percent significant criteria.

The eliminated variables identified from the hierarchical model are courage, Command, Interpersonal relationship, decision making, Knowledge, Intelligence, Self-Management and Lead by example.

Conclusion: The above linear regression equation identified the impact of different dimensions on emotional intelligence. Based on the noteworthy value of experiment of different eight models framed in experiment support a high impact and influence of traits on Emotional Intelligence.

The result produces a strong evidence to disown the statement of null hypothesis and the result can be interpreted as there is a strong influence of traits on Emotional intelligence. The Emotional Intelligence of Regional party leaders are highly leveraged to the other dimensions identified in leaders of regional party.

9. CONCLUSIONS

1. The Emotional Intelligence is the detected as an important dimension or trait of any political leader, the following are findings are marked below to improve the leadership effectiveness of select regional party political leaders by linking Emotional Intelligence.
2. The highest mean attains by the factor which is connecting to emotional intelligence is 'For a leader promise and action must be coherence' the mean value noticed for this element is 3.88.
3. The above said factor highlighting the fact that leader who fulfilled the promise made to the public get the good recognition and support from the public.
4. The least mean 3.02 observed for the factor linked to emotional intelligence is "competence prevail trust in leader" the confidence on leader capabilities is less influencing the leadership effectiveness of regional political party leadership compare with other factors comes under dimension of Emotional Intelligence.
5. The Consummate adjusted R^2 0.964 extracted between the variables from linear regression equation integrating to emotional intelligence to other dimensions is Astuteness i.e., 96.4% variance is observed between these two dimensions, this can be further interpreted as the qualities pertaining to Astuteness is having impact on emotional intelligence of regional political leader.

6. The significant arrived from linear regression experiment connecting dimensions Astuteness, statesmanship, strategy, transparency, relationship management, accountability, creativity and command to emotional intelligence is 0.00 at five percent level of significance i.e., all these stated dimensions are directly influencing the emotional intelligence of leader.
7. It is found based on the significance which is identified as higher than 0.05 at five percent critical value for the dimensions Interpersonal relationships, Knowledge, self-management and allied dimensions are not influencing the emotional intelligence of regional political party leadership.
8. The highest tolerance 0.178 extracted from the linear equation in between elements Interpersonal relationship and emotional intelligence this signs high multi collinearity is observed between these two dimensions. High multi collinearity indicates the less or negligible correlation between the dimensions Interpersonal relationships and emotional intelligence.
9. The remarkable value obtained from the linear regression equation linking to the variables strategy, statesmanship and transparency to emotional intelligence is noticed as 0.00 this state's these three dimensions of leaders are most influencing factors showing impact on emotional intelligence of regional political leader.
10. The negative co-efficient are noticed for the dimensions transparency -0.095, Accountability - 0.152 and command -0.042 indicates the negative correlation with the Emotional intelligence of leader.
11. The extreme β 0.982 value is noticed between the dimensions emotional intelligence and Astuteness i.e., a percent change in value of emotional intelligence resulted 0.982 change in the factor Astuteness this noticed high dependency of emotional intelligence on leadership qualities of Astuteness.

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